

Techno-economic Analysis of Sustainable Terrestrial, Aerial and Space 6G Networks

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Abstract—The emerging integration of Terrestrial Network (TN) and Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) Base Stations (BSs) is anticipated in 6G to cope with the ever-increasing capacity demands, with the optimal decision on which to deploy and where to be one of the main problems. In this paper, we focus on minimizing the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) of the different terrestrial, aerial and space BS types while satisfying the 6G traffic requirements. Although related work focuses on the improvement of resource allocation and network automation, the financial aspects of the new access nodes and their effectiveness remain a lesser topic, which is thorough analyzed in this study. In particular, a detailed energy and cost analysis model is proposed for the 6G access network, which is expected to be the main energy bottleneck, employing different BS types and analyzing their main differences. Then, the total TCO is evaluated for each BS type under different use case scenarios. The provided results demonstrate that NTNs can achieve up to 4.4 times lower TCO in coverage driven scenarios, proving that an integrated TN-NTN architecture is of vital importance for 6G.

Index Terms—6G, Green Deal, Energy Efficiency, UAV, HAPS, Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO), Low Earth Orbit (LEO), Medium Earth Orbit (MEO), Space, Total Cost of Ownership (TCO).

I. INTRODUCTION

The next generation of wireless mobile communications, widely referred to as Sixth Generation (6G), is about to greatly enhance and extend the use case scenarios that 5G introduced half a decade ago. The extreme data rates it will offer, along with the worldwide coverage, will be the key enablers for new technologies to emerge and the existing ones to become even more efficient. The possibilities that 6G will offer to future mobile networks will be a lot sharper than those of 5G, enhancing the already existing ones, like Immersive Communication, extending enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) and Hyper Reliable and Low-Latency Communication, extending Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communication (URLLC), or creating new ones, like Artificial Intelligence and Communication and Integrated Sensing and Communication [1].

In contrast with the previous generations, 6G foresees the incorporation of non-terrestrial base stations (BSs), both aerial and space ones. These new types of BSs, will lead to high BS heterogeneity, thus resulting into new challenges. Exploring each of the new BS categories, the future aerial nodes will consist of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) and

High Altitude Platform Stations (HAPS). On the other hand, satellite nodes are divided into three categories, according to their altitude above the Earth: a) Low Earth Orbit (LEO), b) Medium Earth Orbit (MEO) and c) Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO) satellites. LEO satellites are considered from 450 km to 2000 km altitude, MEO are from 2000 km to just under 35786 km, and last GEO ones are always at 35786 km altitude and match Earth's rotation period.

This plethora of different BSs is expected to meet the new goals set for 6G offering ubiquitous connectivity anywhere and anytime. The extremely high data rates 6G will offer will enable new possibilities for every industry and allow them to expand to never before seen horizons. One of the key enabling technologies for capacity growth is the network densification. Nevertheless, it is expected to be accompanied with a high energy and cost impact, especially in the case of the access network, which is considered the main energy bottleneck for the emerging 6G [2]. Hence, proper network planning is needed for highly cost-efficient and truly sustainable 6G.

Counting these and many more new possibilities that will be enabled with the expansive new network architecture, a principal factor that must be taken into account is the whole energy-efficient and economically affordable BSs. Considering this overall network conversion from a terrestrial-only perspective to a full three layered network consisting of ground, air and space domains, each with their own individual BS types and states, it is implied that a more intrusive explanation and an analytic cost analysis of these new types of BSs are needed. Each one of them will significantly differ both in Capital (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditure (OPEX), meaning that in some use case scenarios some of them will serve better and more efficiently than others. As a result, a detailed comparative study of different network deployment options is needed, taking into account both energy- and cost-efficiency metrics and factors affecting them, to derive useful insights for sustainable 6G network planning.

A. Related work and Contribution

The economic efficiency of 6G is a vital factor and metric of the next generation mobile networks, being characterized by the need of high financial resource efficiency while minimizing any potential leaks. In [3]–[9], the authors propose different

techniques and technologies that are expected to enhance the emerging networks, but their focus point is to simplify and automate the network, without considering the overall Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) of the network itself. In [3], the authors propose and evaluate a Machine Learning (ML) method, called Transfer Learning (TL) that simplifies the use of ML by enabling the reusability of already existing models, enhancing the network to be more efficient in delay-tolerant tasks. Authors in [4] compare different LEO satellite mega constellations for global coverage and resource allocation with the use of AI, without considering the use of the aerial domain or the TCO of each solution. In [5], the use of network slicing is discussed and simulated in order to improve the spectrum resource allocation for better network performance in terrestrial-only networks. In [6], the authors focus on maximizing the energy efficiency on air-ground integrated networks and propose a Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) technique, which is compared with other State-of-the-Art (SoA) solutions, excluding, however, the space domain. A joint optimization problem is stated in [7], where a UAV with Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) capabilities is deployed focusing on maximizing energy efficiency and comparing the proposed algorithm with several SoA algorithms, although still not considering the space domain. Authors in [8] study the orchestration problem in a LEO satellite network via Software Defined Networking (SDN) and compare their proposed algorithm with different benchmarks focusing on load fairness and serving capacity, ignoring the TCO of such deployments and the integrated space-air-ground domain. In [9], the authors combine SDN and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) in space-air-ground integrated networks to improve its performance and automation, while comparing it with different states of AI inclusion to show its significance, not taking into account the long-term financial needs for this deployment.

Nevertheless, the aforementioned works either fail to consider all three layers (ground, air and space) [6], [7] or do not target TCO reduction [9] or both [3]–[5], [8], and thus their high cost efficiency performance cannot be guaranteed. To that end, in this paper, the differences between the wide range of BSs that 6G will bring are detailed and discussed together with their potential use cases as well as employed frequency bands for each one of them.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section II presents the employed energy and cost models, while Section III describes the differences between the proposed BSs that will be available in 6G. In Section IV, the proposed solutions are compared under different scenarios and useful insights are derived, while Section V concludes the paper.

II. ENERGY AND COST MODELS

In this section, the models used for the energy and cost analysis of the deployed architecture, will be detailed. Particularly, the channel model will be discussed together with the communication performance metrics, as well as the models applicable to the aerial and space domains.

A. Channel Modeling

The SINR (dB) is the ratio of the power of a signal (S) to the power of interference (I) plus noise (N) and is given by:

$$SINR = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{S}{N \cdot I} \right). \quad (1)$$

This equation can be also written in terms of the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) for a particular transmitter-receiver pair (i, j) (in dB) as:

$$SINR_{ij} = SNR_{ij} - 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{I}{N} + 1 \right). \quad (2)$$

The SNR is calculated by considering the transmit power of the BS signal (P_{Tx}), the antenna gains of the transmitter (G_{Tx}) and the receiver (G_{Rx}), subtracting the losses in the transmitter cable (L_{Tcable}), the receiver cable (L_{Rcable}), the total path loss (L_{total}), the thermal noise ($N_{thermal}$) and noise figure (N_f). It is measured in dB and given by:

$$SNR_{ij} = P_{Tx} + G_{Tx} + G_{Rx} - L_{Tcable} - L_{Rcable} - L_{total} - N_{thermal} - N_f. \quad (3)$$

The thermal noise in a system is calculated using Boltzmann's constant (k), the bandwidth (BW) and the temperature (T). This product, when expressed in logarithmic scale is given by:

$$N_{th} = 10 \log_{10} (k \cdot BW \cdot T). \quad (4)$$

The EIRP, in dBW, is given by:

$$EIRP = P_{Tx} + G_{Tx} - L_{Tx}, \quad (5)$$

where P_{Tx} and G_{Tx} is the power and the antenna gain of the transmitter, respectively, and L_{Tx} is the transmitter losses, which can refer to polarization loss, to cable loss, etc. Then, the ratio of the carrier power, C , to the noise spectral power density, N_0 , in dBHz, is given by:

$$\frac{C}{N_0} = EIRP - L_{total} - k + \frac{G}{T}, \quad (6)$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant and is equal to $-228.6 \text{ dBW} \cdot K_{-1} \cdot \text{Hz}^{-1}$. The parameter G/T refers to the figure of merit of the receiver and it is given by subtracting from the receiver antenna gain all the receiver losses, such as polarization loss, feeder loss etc. The SNR in aerial and space links, in dB, can thus be given by:

$$SNR = \frac{C}{N_0} - 10 \log_{10}(BW), \quad (7)$$

where $\frac{C}{N_0}$ is the the ratio of the carrier power, C , to the noise spectral power density and BW is the carrier bandwidth in Hz. The total path loss (L_{total}) in a communication system is the summation of the Free Space Path Loss (FSPL) (L_{FSPL}) and the atmospheric losses (L_{atm}), both measured in decibels (dB), i.e.,

$$L_{total} = L_{FSPL} + L_{atm}. \quad (8)$$

Atmospheric losses (L_{atm}) include various factors that attenuate the signal as it travels through the atmosphere. According to the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) standards

[10], these factors include rain attenuation (L_{rain}), gas attenuation (L_{gas}), fog attenuation (L_{fog}) and scintillation losses (L_{scint}). The total atmospheric loss in dB is equal to:

$$L_{atm} = L_{gas} + \sqrt{(L_{rain} + L_{fog})^2 + L_{scint}^2}. \quad (9)$$

B. Communication Performance Metrics

Spectral Efficiency (SE), in bps/Hz, is a metric of how efficiently the available bandwidth is used, which is given by:

$$SE_{i,u} = \min(N_{TX_i}, N_{RX_u}) \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{N_{RX_u} \cdot SINR_{i,u}}{\min(N_{TX_i}, N_{RX_u})} \right), \quad (10)$$

where N_{TX_i} represents the number of transceiver chains of i and N_{RX_u} the transceiver chains of receiver u . The maximum capacity of a communication channel in bps is:

$$capacity_{max} = BW \cdot SE = BW \cdot \log_2(1 + SINR_{i,u}). \quad (11)$$

C. Energy and Cost Model

Energy efficiency, in bits/Joule, refers to the total number of successfully sent bits divided by the total energy consumed, or equivalently to the total data rate divided by the total power consumption. Hence,

$$EE = \frac{DataRate}{PowerConsumption} \left[\frac{bps}{W} \right] = [bit/J]. \quad (12)$$

The power consumption of a link l is given by:

$$P_l = \sum_{i \in L} N_{TRX_i} (P_{0i} + \Delta_{pi} P_{Ti}), \quad (13)$$

where N_{TRX_i} is the number of transceiver chains in the link, P_{0i} is the power consumed when the link is in idle state, Δ_{pi} is the power slope indicating how the power scales with the increase of the load of the link and P_{Ti} is the transmit power consumption.

Finally, cost efficiency, in bps/EUR/year, refers to the total data rate divided by the total amount of EUR spent for TCO per year, and is given by:

$$CE = \frac{Data\ rate}{TCO\ in\ EUR\ per\ year} \left[\frac{bps}{EUR/year} \right]. \quad (14)$$

III. COMPARISON OF THE DIFFERENT BASE STATIONS

The new types of BSs introduced in 6G will span across terrestrial, aerial, and space layers. Each type comes with its own advantages and disadvantages, depending on the specific use case scenarios. A detailed comparison among these different BS types is illustrated in Table I.

Terrestrial networks, positioned at the lowest altitude compared to aerial and space layers, have the smallest geographical coverage. GEO satellites, in contrast, offer the largest coverage, reaching up to 3,500 km [11], or about one-third of the Earth's surface at maximum coverage. However, due to their high altitude (35,786 km), GEO satellites experience long two-way signal propagation delays of 240 to 280 ms [12], which is almost nine times longer than the 30 to 40 ms delay of LEO satellites [13], which cover a maximum geographical area of

1,000 km with a cell radius of 50 km [14]. HAPS provide geographic coverage of 100 to 200 km per platform and have a shorter propagation delay of 10 ms [12], [15].

In terms of operational duration, UAVs have the shortest lifetime, ranging from 0.3 to 30 hours. As a result, to maintain continuous operation, more than one UAV is needed to allow for recharging cycles. GEO satellites have the longest lifetime, between 15 to 30 years [16], [17], while LEO satellites and airships have lifespans of 5 to 10 years [18], [19].

Regarding payload capacity, UAVs carry the smallest load, whereas space nodes can handle larger payloads. Please note that GEO satellites mainly weigh up to 6,500 kg, whereas LEO ones around 500 kg [12], in contrast to a UAV which normally weighs about a few tens of kilos.

Cost efficiency is a critical factor for an optimal network deployment. TNs using macro cells (gNB for 5G/6G) have a TCO of 168,000 EUR per BS (including OPEX, e.g., spectrum licensing fees and maintenance costs) [15]. Although they have a high TCO for long-distance deployment (30 km), they are a cost-efficient solution for short-distance coverage (e.g., 1 km). On the other hand, Small Cells (SCs) have the lowest TCO, at 30,000 EUR per year per BS [20]. The TCO for (fixed-wing) UAVs varies based on type, quality, and features, averaging 200,000 EUR per BS [21], while HAPS platforms have a TCO of approximately 0.5 million EUR per platform [15], [22].

Satellites incur higher TCO compared to terrestrial and aerial BSs. LEO satellites have a TCO per constellation ranging from 5 to 15 billion EUR with a CAPEX of 25 to 30 billion EUR and around 7,000 EUR/kg launch cost per LEO [12]. For a 1,000 kg LEO satellite, the TCO is 750,000 EUR per satellite. Smaller LEOs, such as Oneweb ones weighing 150 kg, have a TCO of 155,000 EUR per satellite. For the rest of the paper, without loss of generality, we will refer to this type of LEO satellites, as they constitute a more popular solution for 6G due to their higher cost efficiency.

Finally, GEOs require higher launch cost per satellite of approximately 21,000 EUR/kg [12]. Despite this, fewer MEO and GEO satellites than LEO are needed to cover the Earth's surface, resulting in lower overall CAPEX. Consequently, GEO satellites have the lowest TCO from all satellite types.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Scenarios

To illustrate how various deployment options perform across different metrics, we will concentrate our study on two distinct scenarios: a capacity-driven scenario and a coverage-driven scenario, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The first scenario (capacity-driven scenario), focuses on meeting traffic demands based on the required total capacity. In this case, a smaller area of 0.05 km² is considered, with total network capacity needs ranging from 0.1 to 1 Gbps/m², reflecting the capacity demands of Beyond 5G (B5G) networks up to 6G. This scenario is typical of densely populated areas, such as city centers, stadiums, or shopping malls. The second scenario (coverage-driven scenario) focuses on network coverage needs of large areas with low data traffic demands, such as those in rural

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF DIVERSE TYPES OF BASE STATIONS

Characteristic/BS Type	Terrestrial BSs	Fixed-wing UAVs	Hybrid UAVs	Aerostatic HAPS	Aerodynamic HAPS	Satellites
Altitude	0-0.3 km	1-10 km	1-10 km	18-22 km	18-22 km	300-35786 km
Flight Time	N/A	6-12 h	6-12 h	5-10 y (airships)	6-12 months	LEO: 5-10 y, GEO: 15-30 y
Autonomy	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Coverage	Up to 1-2 km	Up to 10 km	Up to 10 km	Up to 500 km per platform	Up to 50 km per platform	LEO: Up to 1000 km, GEO: Up to 3500 km (~1/3 of Earth's surface)
Cell radius	0.1-1 km	0.1-5 km	0.1-5 km	>10 km	>10 km	LEO: 50 km, GEO: >400 km
Two-way delay	<<1 ms	<1 ms	<1 ms	<10 ms	<10 ms	LEO: <40 ms, GEO: 238<t<278 ms
Payload	N/A	5-15 kg	~10 kg	<500 kg	5-20 kg	Average weight: LEO: ~ 500 kg, GEO: 1000 ≤ w ≤ 6500 kg

TABLE II
SIMULATION PARAMETERS OF THE DIFFERENT BASE STATION TYPES USED IN THE EVALUATION RESULTS

Parameters/BS Type	gNB	SC	UAV	HAPS	LEO
P_T (dBm)	{46, 43}	{38, 36}	{32, 28}	{42, 40}	N/A
EIRP density (dBW/MHz)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	4
Frequency (GHz)	{3.5, 30}	{5, 28}	{5, 28}	{2.1, 28}	{20, 28}
Bandwidth (MHz)	{100-400, 500-2000}	{100-600, 500-2000}	{100-600, 500-2000}	{40-200, 500-1000}	{500-1000, 500-2000}
G_{Tx} (dBi)	{32, 36}	{26, 32}	{26, 32}	{28, 42}	{38.5, 42}
G_{Rx} (dBi)	{24, 28}	{20, 24}	{20, 24}	{24, 36}	{24, 32}
N_{Tx}	{128, 256}	{32, 64}	{16, 32}	{64, 128}	{128, 256}
N_{Rx}	{64, 128}	{16, 32}	{16, 32}	{32, 64}	{64, 128}
P_0 (W)	{145, 130}	{6.8, 6}	{2, 1.5}	{1, 0.5}	{1, 0.5}
Δ_p	{4.2, 4.7}	{4, 4.5}	{4, 4.5}	{2, 2.5}	{1, 1}
L_{Tcable} (dB)	1	1	1	1	1
L_{Rcable} (dB)	0.5	0.5	0.5	N/A	N/A
N_f (dB)	{1.5, 4.5}	{2, 4}	{2, 4}	N/A	N/A
G/T (dB/K)	N/A	N/A	N/A	{0, 15}	{10, 15}
Cell Radius (km)	0.5	0.1	1	{5, 2}	{20, 10}
BS Altitude (m)	25	10	10000	20000	600000

areas, which typically have a scattered population with low rate requirements. In this scenario, the total area considered in the simulations ranges from 10 to 100 km².

The parameters values used in the simulation are summarized in Table II. Moreover, every User Equipment (UE) was set to 1.5 meters altitude as an average for each person, availability is 99.999% and rain height is 28.31 mm/h. The simulation environment was MATLAB 2023b and the desktop used had an Intel Core i5-14600K with 32 Gb of RAM. For the UAVs, the fixed-wing ones were chosen as they seem a more reasonable choice for telecom compared to multicopters (which involve higher energy consumption due to their increased number of motors), and given the lack of data for hybrid UAVs, since they are a newer solution to the industry. In the case of HAPS, airships were chosen given their

superior performance, while for HAPS as well as LEOs, two different coverage radius are considered.

B. Results

In order to better understand the cost efficiency of different BS types, Fig. 2 shows a bar chart comparing the cost efficiency per BS, measured in bps per EUR per year. The chart confirms that terrestrial BSs generally perform better in capacity-driven scenarios. However, unlike the previous figure, it identifies SCs (SCs) as the most cost-efficient solution rather than gNBs. The next most efficient BSs are LEO satellites, particularly those operating at higher frequencies, due to their high-capacity capabilities.

1) *Capacity-driven results:* Fig. 3 shows the total number of BSs required per type to meet the total network capacity

Fig. 1. Illustration of the two different simulation scenarios: a capacity-driven (in orange color) and a coverage-driven (in blue color).

Fig. 2. Cost efficiency per base station type measured in bps/EUR/year.

needs. In this scenario, deploying a limited number of gNBs is ideal due to their significant capacity capabilities. The smaller coverage radius of gNBs compared to aerial or space BSs is not a problem given the small area to be covered. Compared to SCs, gNBs offer much higher spectral efficiency and maximum capacity due to superior electronics and fewer antenna space restrictions. The next best solutions are LEOs and HAPS (operating at higher frequencies and bandwidth). According to the figure, LEOs perform slightly better than HAPS because of their higher maximum capacity, resulting in fewer BSs needed to meet the capacity demands. The worst-performing BS is HAPS operating at the lowest frequency range and bandwidth, due to its limited capacity.

In Fig. 4, the TCO per year in EUR is shown for each type of BS in the capacity-driven scenario compared to different total data rate demands. The graph indicates that when network capacity needs are high, the most cost-efficient solution is to deploy terrestrial-only BSs due to their lower overall cost for the necessary number of BSs to achieve the targeted capacity. The next most cost-efficient option is deploying LEO satellites, due to their higher payload, and consequently capacity, capabilities. The least cost-efficient solutions are HAPS and UAVs, which show a significant increase in TCO due to the very high number of BSs required in these scenarios, as detailed in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. Number of required base stations versus the total data rate demand for different base station type deployments under the capacity-driven scenario.

Fig. 4. TCO versus the total data rate demand for different base station type deployments under the capacity-driven scenario.

2) *Coverage-driven results:* Fig. 5 illustrates the total number of required BSs to cover a large region. In this coverage-driven scenario, the best solution is using LEO satellites and HAPS at lower frequencies. Their higher altitude allows them to cover a much larger area than other BS types. In the studied scenario, only one satellite is needed to cover the entire area, whereas TN BSs require dozens or even hundreds in the case of SCs. The two HAPS variants perform differently, with the higher frequency band experiencing significantly greater path loss and atmospheric loss, which limits the signal's ability to travel long distances compared to lower frequencies.

Fig. 6 presents a graph illustrating the TCO per year for various types of BSs in a scenario where covering a large area is the primary objective. In this scenario, satellites are the most favorable option due to their higher altitude, which allows for significantly greater coverage. HAPS at lower frequencies are also a viable option, but their smaller coverage radius compared to satellites results in less overall coverage. Unlike the previous figure, where terrestrial BSs were the best solution, this scenario reveals the opposite. Terrestrial BSs, being near ground level, cannot cover large regions, making them the least cost-efficient solution. Please note that an NTN-only approach using LEO satellites can achieve up to 99% and

Fig. 5. Number of required base stations versus the total targeted coverage area for different base station type deployments under the coverage-driven scenario.

Fig. 6. TCO versus the total targeted coverage area for different base station type deployments under the coverage-driven scenario.

4.4 times lower TCO than a TN-only approach using gNBs and SCs, respectively. The fact that coverage-driven scenarios call for NTN deployments, whereas capacity-driven ones for TN-only solutions, make the integrated TN-NTN architectures a key building block of 6G networks.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we provided a detailed techno-economic analysis of different BS type network deployments, analyzing their TCO under different use case scenarios and requirements. Our results demonstrate that for high-capacity needs, 6G networks will have to mainly rely on TN-only solutions. On the other hand, for coverage of large low-populated areas, aerial and space nodes will play a key role, achieving up to 4.4 times lower TCO than TN-only solutions comprising solely SCs. As a result, a mixture of TN and NTN deployments is anticipated in 6G, justifying the need for an integrated 3D 6G architecture.

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